

Knowledge and Skills for Library and Information Science

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Abstract

This paper is a systematic literature review of LIS professionals' knowledge and competence for the library to maintain its relevance in the existing digital world. The library has experienced many changes attributed to technology, and as a result, the skills and knowledge that employers require from LIS professionals have changed. Indeed, literature has revealed that employers are looking for a range of skills, grouped into three main categories; generic skills, personal skills, and discipline-specific skills.

Disciplinary skills are foundational, and therefore every job applicant is expected to have them. However, this study found that what sets candidates apart is the generic skills, which are the skills gained through experience and the ability to embrace changes and prepare for a changing library's future challenges. As a result, most employers who advertise for LIS jobs are looking for flexible candidates and adapt to changing environments.

The study also has implications for the employers and educators alike, who need to collaborate to make the LIS professions more attractive to students. Research indicates the number one motivation for students pursuing a career in LIS is the love for books and the satisfaction with the job. The first step towards making LIS more attractive should be to remodel and re-engineer LIS programs to conform to the industry's demands, besides marketing the course and highlighting the service that libraries provide in a digital world.

Keywords: LIS, Master in Library Information Science, Generic Skills, and discipline-specific skills

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Knowledge and Skills for Library and Information Science

1.0 Introduction

A library is any curated collection of information sources and any other resources, either digital or hardcopy, that is kept for posterity and the benefit of a community of users. Modern libraries have integrated technology in their services to offer unrestricted access to information in many formats not previously offered (Nonthacumjane, 2011). The skills and knowledge required for the management of the modern library and information are evolving with the rate at which libraries adopt the technology. Librarians and information custodians in libraries are working on an exciting transition and developments in the 21st century, which has seen a shift in the face and definition of a library (Orme, 2008). The 21st century has been demarcated as the age of information, where holding the right facts at the right time can mean a great difference (Gordon, 2005).

In recent years, discussion on the expertise and skills required in the modern contemporary library has become a hot topic in library literature. In various library sectors, the librarian requirements of the 21st century have been under review in terms of the educational requirements and the kind of available professional development resources (Murray, 2015). The LIS sector changes are not new because libraries and informational requirements have evolved over the centuries (Gordon, 2005). However, the pace of the change and the rate at which the LIS profession has been affected has necessitated the discussion.

Most libraries have a virtual aspect where famous publications have been converted to digital formats and accessed via websites. Social media proliferation and the growth of smartphones and other mobile devices have completely altered libraries' face, which means that the skills needed in library information science (LIS) are changing (Partridge, Lee & Munro,

2020). Transformation in the LIS space requires a crop of LIS professionals to effectively and efficiently manage the vast amount of archived information each day. To illustrate the scale of information that librarians manage, the Library of Congress based in Washington, the biggest and most equipped library in the entire world by volume, receives about 15000 items and adds more than 10,000 items to its collection each day (Library of Congress, 2021). The same statistic is replicated in major libraries around the world.

Orme (2008) opines that the knowledge and competence for the new cohort of librarians can be categorized into two; which are discipline-specific acquaintance, which are the skills that especially relates to LIS; generic skills which are relevant in all jobs, and personal competencies which are the general attitudes, traits, characters and values that can make a person thrive in the LIS space. The discussion on the different competences that are required for contemporary LIS professionals has led to the term librarian 2.0, which is a term that combines nine characteristics that are relevant for modern LIS (Murray, 2015). These competencies are technology, user focus, communication, evidence-based practice, teamwork, business-oriented, personal traits, learning, and education (Partridge, Lee & Munroe, 2020).

This paper explores the competencies and the knowledge that employers are looking for in library information science professionals. The paper also summarizes four key skills critical in LIS and how they can attract a new crop of professionals. Finally, some of the issues that graduates face, which lead to low enrollment in LIS courses, are summarized and how these challenges and biases can be overcome. Planning in terms of LIS's requisite competencies is an integral part of ensuring that the LIS sector grows. Therefore, an understanding of the competencies required in the current LIS space is concern for both employers and educators.

2.0 Literature review

2.1 Library 2.0 and the evolution of the library

The fast evolution of technology, and changes in the areas of learning and methods of teaching, have impacted libraries worldwide. The Library of Congress, for instance, current processes and curates over 15000 information sources in a different format. The creation of novel knowledge products in schools and colleges, such as subject portals and the creation of various types of publications in schools and organizations, has led to the requirement for a new definition of the library.

Lance (2008) remarks that the "convergence of exponential increases in computing, storage, online sensors, and bandwidth" has enabled collaboration on research by scientists in different fields, which has led to the rise of terms such as eResearch and eScience. The revolutionary developments in the research and academic space have led to a definition of libraries that accommodate scientists' needs in the new contexts of eScience and eResearch. Therefore, knowledge preservation has risen a very sought-after skill that modern librarians now need to have.

Nonthacumjane (2011) states that for the library of the 21st century to capture effectively, curate, share and preserve traditional books as well as digital knowledge, definitions such as Library 2.0, Library 3.0 electronic publishing, and other systems of digital content preservation need to be understood and applied in LIS. Orme (2008) opines that the digitization of libraries has a great impact on the skills and competence of LIS experts. Therefore, new skills are looked-for to tackle the challenges faced by libraries in an information explosion era.

2.2 Assessment for the need for new skills and knowledge in a fast-changing LIS space

The Bureau of Labor Statistics predicts that librarians and library media specialists' employment will grow by about 5% between 2019 and 2029, which is a much faster rate than the

average job growth rate in other occupations (BLS, December 4, 2020). This is because communities are increasingly turning to library services for various services, driving the demand for librarians and library media specialists to help clients locate resources and find information. Additionally, in a 2011 blog post, Bonfield (2011) states that LIS schools are increasingly graduating more and more students while the LIS job market is at capacity.

Several researchers such as Myburgh (2003) and Choi & Rasmussen (2009) have published findings that show a proliferation of library job titles, from just 19 in 1988 to over 33 unique positions in 2009. The researchers cite that integrating emerging technologies in the LIS space has been the cause of these new titles. Choi & Rasmussen (2009) remarks that employers are increasingly requesting sophisticated technological knowledge such as building online instruction tutorials, computer programming, web design, and knowledge of library management systems.

The discussion on the skills and the knowledge required for LIS has become important, especially as a demographic shift is happening in almost every job sector, where baby boomers are retiring from the workforce, while Millennials and Gen Zs are joining the workforce. According to Husain & Mazin (2013), the average age of LIS professionals is between 45 and 55. Strategies at attracting new entrants into the profession should be a top priority for employers and LIS professional associations. Additionally, technology is transforming the LIS space, with a strong incentive to use I.T. and create more inclusive virtual learning environments. Other digital information system services such as podcasting, Wikis, and blog spaces have also been added under LIS management in many institutions. Therefore, LIS's changing face calls for a review of the skills and competencies needed by employers.

Ratledge & Sproles (2017) states that as libraries continue to adopt new technology, systems librarians' roles and responsibilities have been transformed, from simply managing library

databases and ILS to new roles such as creating content for online users. Therefore, employers seek candidates with additional skills such as customer service, problem-solving, technology implementation, and a digital collection. Ocholla & Shongwe (2013) states that a key pillar for skills and competencies developed in the LIS space is the collaboration piece between professionals, educators, and employees, in creating solutions to developing a motivated LIS workforce that can flourish in a high-pressured environment and respond to changes taking place in the LIS space with a positive attitude.

Myburgh (2003) states that the LIS space needs a wider theoretical framework, which is not necessarily based on technical knowledge. Rather, what is required is a knowledge inventory that will enable the new worker joining the profession to deal with teething challenges during his or her career. This sentiment is echoed by Van House & Sutton (1993). They state that LIS education does not necessarily mean that the current LIS programs in colleges and universities need to stay the same. The knowledge base gathered over the centuries should be preserved and applied to develop new tools to be applied in new problem areas.

Further, Van House & Sutton (1993) commented that for the LIS space to thrive in the 21st century, a new niche needs to be found where unique skills and knowledge can be developed, specifically library management. This is necessitated by the struggle between LIS and other professions and academic disciplines over information science functions. Middleton (2003) states that the best way to study the acquaintance and skills required for the modern LIS space, is to first assess employers' needs. Myburgh (2003) also states that the changes in libraries' functions, spurred by technological advancement, have made it necessary to re-evaluate the needed skills and competence to drive LIS forward.

The Special Libraries Association (2019) has identified the role that emerging technologies such as Blockchain and A.I. may play in the LIS space, which calls for employers to re-evaluate the required skills recruits. Khan & Bhatti (2017) opine that modern librarians need to be first and foremost competent in the management of digital publications and other types of electronic content as the LIS space moves further into digital systems. Further, the researchers noted that higher education institutions should fine-tune their training programs to include digital content management training.

The interplay of the various factors that have been discussed above necessitates an evaluation of the skills and competencies necessary to have to succeed in LIS.

2.3 Skills and knowledge for the current LIS space

The states of the LIS job market indicate that the field is competitive while jobs are scarce. The majority of positions being advertised require work experience. Further, Forbes, in 2012 ranked library and information science as one of the worst Master's degrees in pay and attractiveness (Forbes, 2012), which further dampens graduates' hopes of ever succeeding in the profession. The state of the LIS job market and the skills and knowledge required in different library space roles have been studied extensively over the years (Sinclair, 2009). Several sources have indicated that most entry-level LIS positions require candidates to have at least a Master's Degree. Simultaneously, other researchers such as Marshall et al. (2009) cite studies that have indicated that even the prerequisite of a Master's degree is not enough in the LIS job market presently.

Raju (2014) states that the various reliable method to assess the competencies needed for LIS job roles is by the means of job advertisements content analysis in a chosen period. The research articles reviewed, such as (Clyde 2002, Oreme, 2008, Choi & Rasmussen, 2009, and

Byschowski et al. 2010), all employ the content analysis technique. Raju (2016) states that triangulation yields more credible results, where content analysis, interviewing of LIS professionals in the field, and looking at other jobs data can be used.

The literature review in this section intentionally categorizes skills and proficiencies required by LIS employers into three categories; generic skills, personal skills, and disciplinary skills. This is aimed at making clear distinctions between these skills to highlight the importance of each. Researchers such as Patridge & Hallam (2004) have combined generic and personal skills into a single category, which is not wrong, given that Reeves & Hahn (2010) states that generic and personal skills have just recently become important due to the changes that technology and other factors have brought into the library space.

Wise, Hanninger & Kennan (2011) have found out that being multi-skilled is becoming crucial for the new cohort of LIS professionals. Academic qualifications are still important, but more and more, employers are swinging towards personal and generic skills as a way to weed out candidates during interviews. All the literature that has been in this paper stress that all the three categories of skills are so closely intertwined that it is not easy to strip each component apart. Uniquely, job experience, which is neither discipline-related nor a generic skill, has been highlighted by Orme (2008) and Reeves & Hahn (2010) as a core requirement that employers are putting so much emphasis on. This is perhaps because there is a mismatch between the training students receive and the skills that employers are looking for. Therefore, employers prefer to avert the cost of re-training by hiring workers who essentially plug and play.

2.3.1. Disciplinary skills

Raju (2016) defines the disciplinary or professional skills as the core competencies gained through educational training and enables the LIS professional to perform the task they are

employed to. Raju (2016) questions whether the pendulum in the LIS job requirements is swinging further into the disciplinary skills space where LIS workers have to rely on technology to achieve efficiency.

Choi & Rasmussen (2009) conducted a deep analysis into LIS job advertisements in the U.S. from 1999 to 2007 and summarized the most common competencies and skills that are required by employers in a technologically driven library space, while Triumph & Baile (2015), researched the terminologies and descriptive words used in adverts looking to fill vacancies in libraries, in the United States from 2011 to 2015. Choi & Rasmussen (2009) found that understanding metadata and digital content management knowledge are some of the top skills that employers were looking for. The generic skills that employers were looking for include critical thinking, teamwork, effective communication, and interpersonal skills, and problem-solving.

Bronstein (2015) found that library and information science jobs advertised in Israel tended to emphasize information services skills, especially skills related to information organization. The study also extended to the survey of courses that were offered in institutions of higher learning, and the results showed that LIS programs prepared the student to work in technologically enabled environments without an emphasis on the development of personal competencies, which creates a mismatch between what students are trained for and what employers expect.

Clyde (2002) found that job advertisements for different academic, public, and special libraries still required traditional LIS skills, such as the knowledge of current bibliographic instruction, specified education that involved developing training manuals for other library staff. However, there was an emphasis on additional competencies, chiefly generic capabilities such as problem-solving skills and flexibility.

In a more recent study, Ahmed & Sheikh (2020) found out that LIS roles that were advertised tended to "blend" positions of responsibilities, while the number and the specialization of positions rose. Shank (2006) also conducted a similar study, where he defined a blended librarian as "an academic librarian who combines the traditional skills and roles of a librarian with the information technologist's hardware/software skills, and the instructional or education designer's ability to apply technology appropriately in the teaching-learning process." Both Ahmed & Sheikh (2020) and Shank (2006) state that most job advertisements for library positions for a blended librarian require that the candidate possess strong computer skills and be conversant with emerging instructional technologies.

Bychowski et al. (2010), in a study of science librarian positions in two time periods of 1998-2001 and 2008-2010, concluded that science librarianship's roles and responsibilities have changed over the two periods. Yet, the skills and competencies that were expected from candidates to the job positions have not changed much. The study found that the qualifications still emphasized grounded library science knowledge and people skills. The findings of Bychowski et al. (2010) contrast to the findings of Kim, Addom & Stanton (2011), which found that the job requirements in terms of the skills needed for entry-level positions for eResearch librarians have changed over the same period, to include highly specialized skills such as database design, working knowledge of scientific research, project management, and information system management among others.

Triumph & Beile (2015), in a study of LIS job advertisements, found that the single qualification that has remained constant is the ALA-accredited MLS, which is deemed to be a foundational requirement for academic library positions. However, research into the LIS space finds out that the ALS-accredited MLS is losing ground to technology-oriented skills, which are

being preferred by a wider array of employers. Additionally, Triumph & Beile (2015) found that over 94.8 percent of jobs advertised in the period under study required candidates to have an ALA-accredited MLS. The study also states that for most positions advertised by academic libraries, a master's degree in LIS from an accredited institution was the single constant requirement in all of the jobs. Cabonero & Dolendo (2013) that the skills requirement depended largely on the segment of the organization. Their study found that in departments such as Administration, human resources, and technology departments such as ICT, new skills such as digital data management, data sets, and external relations were required in addition to traditional skills inherent to librarians.

Triumph & Beile (2015) further found that previous work experience is a highly sought skill and that among the jobs that were studied, 74% required the applicants to have prior work experience. Tewell (2012) reported that in jobs posted between 2010 and 2011, entry-level jobs only accounted for 20.7 percent, supporting Triumph & Beile (2015). Tewell (2012) states that in 53% of LIS entry-level jobs, a minimum of two years' experience in information literacy suggests that those seeking LIS jobs should look at ways of gaining experience through summer internships and volunteering.

In all the studies reviewed, such as Bychowski et al. (2010) and Sinclair (2009), knowledge of foreign language skills is still a requirement in some job advertisements, even though this requirement is declining year by year, as observed by Triumph & Beile (2015). Zhang (2008) reported fewer job positions called for proficiency in foreign languages in 2011 than in 1988. They added that the positions that still require knowledge of foreign languages are mostly cataloging bibliography librarians and special collections.

Triumph & Beile (2015) note that academic library jobs are becoming more and more specialized, which means that the skills required are changing. Ahmed & Sheikh (2020) attribute

this proliferation of new academic library job positions to the impact technology has on LIS. Many jobs being advertised between 2009 and 2019 had technology skills as one of the most vital requirements (Partridge, Lee & Munroe, 2020). It is also worth noting that increasingly, positions across all divisions now require librarians to have computer skills

2.3.2 Generic skills

Raju (2014) examined competencies required for LIS specialists in the the South African LIS job market context. The skills and competencies advertised fell into three categories: professional, generic, and people skills. Partridge & Hallam (2004) refers to the generic skills as the graduate attributes or transferable skills, which are basic life skills that can make a person thrive in any occupation. Orme's (2008) study found that from among the disciplinary, personal, and generic skills, the transferable skills were the most sought after by employers, which resonates with the findings of Clyde (2002) that due to the fluid nature of most jobs in the 21st century, employers are continually looking for individuals who are flexible and who have a capacity for continuous learning.

Partridge & Hallam (2004) also found skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and adaptability to be frequent among the requirements for job positions in the LIS space. Orme (2008) states that this apparent "move to the generic skills" is not accidental. As technology has changed, a proliferation of completely different roles not there a decade ago has occurred. The trend is likely to continue, which requires librarians that can adapt fast to change. However, despite the emphasis on generic skills, Wise, Hanninger & Kennan (2011) are categorical to state that disciplinary skills are still the foundational requirements by LIS employers. Even Orme (2008) puts in a caveat in his study and observes that disciplinary skills were found among the top 20 most sought out skills in the job advertisement literature reviewed.

Studies by Middleton (2003), Orme (2008), and Reeves & Hahn (2010), have found that communication skills ranked very highly among the generic skills, while Choi & Rasmussen (2009) made a similar observation about the need for interpersonal skills. These researchers attribute this interest in interpersonal and communication skills to how digital projects are done, where interpersonal and communication competences are key in collaboration on projects.

Riley-Huff & Rholes (2011) argues that technology skills that are not directly applied in a traditional library space, such as web development, can be categorized as generic skills, which is why candidates who possess these skills are attractive LIS employers. The researchers extend the same treatment to managerial skills. However, most researchers discuss technology skills under disciplinary requirements because there is a close relationship between digital skills and the move towards Library 2.0 and Library 3.0, which are both concepts that imply technology integration with traditional library services. Similarly, Sinclair (2009) categorized managerial skills under disciplinary skills because of digital content and data management.

A study by Sinclair (2009) found out that for a blended librarian position, subject expertise, administrative skills, and leadership skills appeared more frequently and were emphasized compared to skills specific to the position, such as knowledge of LIS standards. Tanloet & Tuamsuk (2011) did research on the academic librarian job market in Thailand. The researchers studied the changing LIS space to predict LIS professionals' skills and competencies between 2010 and 2019. The study concluded that there were eight knowledge areas that LIS professionals would require in that decade mostly revolved around information technology in addition to information organization skills and research and user studies. The study adds that 11 key skills would be teamwork, problem-solving, teaching and instructional design, conceptual thinking, and

knowledge management. The study also concluded that service-mindedness, adaptability, flexibility, self-motivation, and leadership were the core personal skills required.

2.3.3. Personal competencies

Personal attributes are the inherent values in individuals. They are the attitudes and the values that define the person. Personal skills are also called people skills, and they are not easily taught in a classroom. They are skills that enable a person to work with others and include flexibility, adaptability, and work under minimal supervision.

Nonthamcumjane (2011) established that most employers are looking for adaptability, flexibility, and reflective thinking as the main personal competencies sought by employers in the Australian LIS job market. Wise, Henninger & Kennan (2011) examined the changing landscape of roles of reference librarians and found out that the number of responsibilities related to the position increased from 10.65 to 14.07 in the 10 years between 1991 and 2001. The additional four roles were technology-related, including email-reference services, online tutorials, and web page design. The study postulated that Library 2.0 and Library 3.0 had added an average of 3.5 to 4.75 roles to the average librarian position.

Choi & Rasmussen (2009) states that personal skills such as learning continuously, adaptability, and flexibility are becoming more important in the LIS profession. Orme (2008) adds that the ability to be self-motivated and remain enthusiastic are also great personal skills to have, while Nonthacumjane (2011) adds reflective thinking and responsiveness to others' needs. Sinclair (2009) states that personal skills and especially adaptive skills cannot be emphasized enough because technology is transforming almost every occupation. Therefore, the ability to cope with changes is becoming of the core skills that any employer is looking for.

3.0. Closing the gap between training and employer expectations in the LIS space

Studies by researchers such as Nonthacumjane (2011) have highlighted the skills gap between LIS graduates' training and employers' expectations. This is not unique to the LIS space because Malik & Venkatraman (2017) and DuPre & Williams (2011) have highlighted the great divide between skills employers are looking for and the skills taught in universities. As Orme (2008) states, technology is changing the LIS profession so fast that discipline-specific skills are becoming less relevant than generic and personal skills. Partridge & Hallam (2004) combines generic skills and personal competencies and includes technology-related skills into this category. In those library jobs where traditional library services such as referencing and cataloging are enabled by technology, graduates need to go the extra mile and acquire knowledge on library management software management.

For the LIS environment to serve a changing society, educators need to assess the qualities that employers seek to design programs that prepare students for the workplace. Valarakshmi (2006) studied the gap between skills that employers look for and the training graduates get by focusing on alumni's perspectives of various colleges and universities in India and employers' perspectives, which were public and academic libraries. The study found that so concerned were libraries and information science employers that some have set up in-house training for new graduates joining the field and the already existing workforce.

Departments of LIS at various universities are also cognizant of the LIS profession's changing nature and employers' demands. As a result, Valarakshmi (2006) found that most universities in India modify their LIS courses to keep their curricula relevant for the emerging skill demands relating to new responsibilities in old settings. Warraich (2008) observes that LIS academicians have become aware of the gap in LIS graduates' skills and are already updating their curriculum to produce graduates who can thrive in a changing LIS job marketplace. Other literature

such as Valarakshami (2006), Mammo (2007), and Stephens & Hamblin (2006) that studied the perception of alumni and employers about the curriculum of LIS and employability found that a postgraduate LIS qualification is desirable to most employers.

Simon & Taylor (2011) used focus groups selected from among students to study the motivations for choosing LIS careers. The study found that personal and professional aspirations formed a complex play of why students choose to study LIS. Other students mentioned that they had previous library work experience, while the MLS degree's perceived value and the salary that comes with a library position were other attractions.

A study by Alansari (2011) on LIS schools' alumni found that quite a significant number choose the career because of a love for books they developed in elementary and high school. In the same study, some individuals mentioned that they got into a LIS career because they perceived it to be an interesting field. Another survey by Ard et al. (2006) among University of Alabama MLIS students found that the number one motivation for students choosing the LIS career path was job satisfaction, followed closely by compensation.

In a follow-up study of the Ard et al. (2006) study at the University of Alabama, Talylor, Perry, Barton & Spencer (2010) utilized the same questionnaire and found that the biggest motivator for choosing an MLIS course was its attractiveness as a career and the general love for being in a "space surrounded by books."

This literature review has looked at both the employer and employee perspective of what skills and knowledge are needed in the modern digitally-enabled library and students' motivations from the study this systematic literature review, educators can look inward at the design of their programs to ascertain whether the training they are offering meets the requirements of employers in the workplace.

4.0 Conclusion and the impact of the paper on the wider profession

The speed at which technology is changing has led to an explosion in information, which has forced libraries to find ways of managing the vast information that comes to their door each day. Skills that were not necessary a decade ago, such as digital information curation and knowledge of learning management systems, are now in great demand. Additionally, new ways of communicating research have led to concepts such as eResearch, which poses a challenge for librarians. Information professionals and educators have been forced to rethink training to fit their curricula to employers' needs.

From the literature review, it is apparent that the competencies required for LIS professionals and graduates joining the field to effectively work in the era of Library 2.0 and Library 3.0 is a combination of three categories of skills, which are discipline-specific skills generic, and the personal skills. In the literature, generic skills seem to be in favor with a majority of employers since discipline skills are gained through training. The generic skills are gained through experience in a job, while the personal skills are the people skills and personal attitudes that make a person work and relate well with others.

Like any other occupation, technology has greatly shifted LIS, and therefore technology skills are becoming more and more common as a requirement in job advertisements. Most of the emerging technology requirements are a re-packaging of the traditional library skills with a twist of technology, which makes generic skills such as adaptability and the ability to learn quickly on the job really important for current and future LIS professionals. This systematic study's implications transcend merely highlighting the skills and knowledge needed for a job in the LIS space (Ahmed & Sheik, 2020). Another intention was to draw out lessons for a wider audience, especially the library and information science training side.

Research into the motivations for choosing a career in LIS has lessons for educators and employers alike. The most common reason cited by students pursuing Master's degrees in LIS reveals that interest is the most prominent factor. Educators can therefore do more to market their courses and programs to a wider audience.

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